

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING DURING THE PANDEMIC COVID-19 IN MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explores motivation towards English language learning among primary school students. The respondents of this study were 42 English teachers from UNITAR International University and teachers teaching English language in Sekolah Kebangsaan, Sekolah Jenis Kebangsaan (Cina), and international schools. Seven close-ended survey questions were given to understand teachers' motivation strategies for students' online English language learning. A quantitative method was approached in this study. The survey data were analyzed to interpret the findings. This study's findings have revealed that nearly similar numbers of participants do not agree on the effectiveness of online teaching in this Covid-19 outbreak. The result can be concluded that teachers' encouragement and efforts in motivating students' English language learning in online classes turned out more positively. An average of 52% shows that teachers motivated their students' English language learning very well in online classes. It can be seen clearly that teachers are exerting themselves to motivate their students' online learning with varied strategies and learning resources such as online learning tools, online platforms, game-based learning, the adaptation of authentic materials, praises, and rewards.

Keywords: online teaching, motivation, English language

INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 Pandemic challenged every sector, mainly the educational sector for more than a year. The government's decision to the school closure has left a great impact on teachers' and students' face-to-face teaching and learning process. As a way of preventing the serious spread of Covid-19 among students, the government has forced schools including elementary, secondary, and high schools as well as universities and colleges to organize online teaching and learning sessions. As a new way of learning, the students are having to adopt the new learning process which is based on online learning platforms such as Google Meet, Google Classroom, Zoom, and so on. Motivation is key to successful online learning. Motivation describes the wants or needs that direct behavior toward a goal (Spielman, Dumper, Jenkins, Lacombe, Lovett & Pearlmutter, 2017).

The online English learning process in this Pandemic is an indifferent track compared with English language learning in classroom circumstances. Online learning is not as interactive as the physical classroom. However, the motivational support for students from their teachers would help to figure

out their motivational factors to reach out the successful online learning. By knowing the students' interests and needs in online English learning, teachers could implement some effective teaching strategies to motivate and stimulate their active online learning. A smart option selected by every teacher to conduct their English lesson is by utilizing multiple online learning tools. It is one of the great strategies to enhance students' motivation in online learning and the results are much more positive for better learning among students. Teacher-recommended ESL websites are suitable to learn the English language (Amutan, Ching, Maruthal & Ling, 2020).

One of the main reasons for the discouragement of students' willingness to learn is caused by teachers' presentation in teaching (Minda, 2020). Therefore, this study aims to investigate on the following research question of how does online learning affect students' motivation toward English language learning?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation is an important aspect of the learning process. It will impact directly how every student learns. The impact of the motivation on a student can be seen when it increases the student's energy level, the student's thinking process, the learning patterns, persistence in reaching a specific goal, etc. Highly motivated students are generally engaged in activities spontaneously and actively and enjoy the learning process without any expectation of external rewards (Skinner & Belmont, 1993). Teachers are playing an important role to make sure every student is involved and actively participated in the online learning process.

There are two types of motivation according to human development professionals: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Research by Legault (2016) stated that intrinsic motivation is a natural human tendency that can be found within the individual. Intrinsic motivation occurs when students are actively engaged in the learning process because of the internal rewards such as their love and own interest in particular subjects and the whole learning process. However, extrinsic motivation is driven by the individual's surroundings and behavior to perform a task and learn new things because of external rewards or avoidance of punishment. Extrinsically motivated students might not genuinely enjoy learning something, but the external rewards of a pay rise motivate them to continue or accomplish. Many teachers extrinsically motivate their students to accomplish some tasks in online classes. Regardless of their efforts, many parents and students claimed that the online teaching and learning process did not work well. The research by Koifman (2020) stated there are some factors that make students refuse to study online including students being bored, afraid of making mistakes, using their own devices to play games, chatting with friends only, being distractible, not interested in studying, having Specific Education Needs (SEN), etc.

For successful online learning, students must be well organized, possess good technology knowledge, and be self-motivated. Young learners are facing more difficulties in online learning. One of the solutions suggested by Fazinic (2015) in his study, the student-centered learning strategies with the use of videos and online learning activities were offered the opportunity for new relationships among teachers and students as well as providing the new classroom management strategies (as cited in Koifman, 2020). Adelsberger (2020) stated students need intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to learn regardless of the physical classroom or online classes. But he stressed on to come up with motivating strategies for students in online classes is much more

difficult compared to the physical classroom which has plenty of ideas to motivate intrinsically and extrinsically. Research by Mese and Sevilen (2021) revealed that students' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in online education was lower compared to physical classrooms. They stated that the reason behind this was a lack of communication between teachers and their peers.

The researcher attempts to make the connection between Krashen's affective filter theory into this study to investigate the possible factors that motivate students' online English language learning. Some of the common problems in students' English language learning include nervousness, ashamed, anxiety, unable to concentrate, etc. Thus, the theory was made up of three main affective variables include motivation, anxiety, and self-confidence.

METHODOLOGY

This study explores on how to motivate the primary students' English learning through online teaching. A quantitative method was adopted in this study. The researcher used a survey questionnaire through Google form as the first instrument to collect data from 42 entries. The questionnaire was developed based on the main research questions of this study which contains two sections. Section one is demographic questions containing teachers' particulars and section two accumulates teachers' motivation strategies for online English language learning. The questionnaire has a five-point scale: strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, and neither agree nor strongly agree. The questionnaires were reviewed by the supervisor for validation purposes before distributing to the participants. The expert review resulted in minor changes, modifications, and deletion of several questions.

Teachers from UNITAR International University and Teachers teaching the English language in Sekolah Kebangsaan, Sekolah Jenis Kebangsaan (Cina), and international schools were approached to take part in the survey.

Finally, the researcher collected frequency and percentage to state the conclusion. The results were presented using table forms whereby the conclusions were presented descriptively.

RESULTS

The data gained from the survey was analyzed well to make the connection and answer the research questions. Teachers from UNITAR International University and teachers teaching the English language in Sekolah Kebangsaan, Sekolah Jenis Kebangsaan (Cina), and international schools were approached to participate in the study. Overall, 42 entries of the survey were used in the study to find the answers on how online learning affects students' motivation towards English language learning.

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHIC

This section presents the basic information of the survey respondents. The table below shows the information related to respondents' age group, gender, academic qualification, and teaching experience.

Table 1. Personal particulars of respondents

VARIABLES	CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Gender	Male	1	2.4
	Female	41	97.6
Age group	20-25	8	19.1
	26-30	5	11.9
	31-35	9	21.4
	36-40	7	16.7
	41-45	7	16.7
	46-50	6	14.3
Academic qualification	SPM	2	4.8
	Diploma	8	19.1
	Degree	21	50
	Master	10	23.8
	Doctorate PhD	1	2.4
Teaching experience	0-5	16	38.1
	6-10	7	16.7
	11-15	6	14.3
	16-20	9	21.4
	21-25	2	4.8
	26-30	2	4.8
	31 above	-	-

Table 1 represented the personal particulars of the respondents categorized according to their gender, age group, academic qualification, teaching experience, present online teaching practice, and their prior online teaching experience. A total of forty-two respondents consisted of 1 male teacher (2.4%) and 41 female teachers (97.6%). The frequency of 9 out of 42 respondents is the highest (21.4%) for teachers categorized between 31-35 years old. The next demographic characteristic is respondents' academic qualifications. The frequency of 21 out of 42 respondents is the highest (50%) possessed qualification of Degree. Followed by the second-highest frequency of 10 respondents with 23.8% possessing the qualification of Master. There are 2 respondents who possessed the qualification of SPM with 4.8%. Whereas 1 out of 42 respondents qualified Doctorate PhD with 2.4%. However, the teaching experiences of respondents are various to their academic qualifications. Based on table 1 above, the highest frequency of 16 respondents which is 38.1% had 0-5 years of teaching experience. This is indicated that the highest group of teachers are considered as new joiners or junior teachers in the education field.

SECTION 2: FACTORS THAT MOTIVATE STUDENTS' ONLINE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

This section of the survey investigated factors that motivate students' online English language learning. This section consisted of 7 questions that will be proving the answers for the research question; how does online learning affect students' motivation toward English language learning? The table below indicates the survey result of section two with the descriptions.

Table 2. Motivation in Online English Language Learning

ITEMS	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
16. I provide sufficient English language online games to motivate my students' learning.		3 (7.2%)	15 (35.7%)	20 (47.6%)	4 (9.5%)
17. I design relevant content with authentic materials to increase my students' interest in English language learning.			11 (26.2%)	26 (61.9%)	5 (11.9%)
18. I frequently praise and reward my students for every task when performed well in online classes.		1 (2.4%)	8 (19%)	21 (50%)	12 (28.6%)
19. I use varied learning materials such as videos and audio to make my English lesson interesting and effective.			8 (19%)	21 (50%)	13 (31%)
20. I encourage interaction and collaboration among students to avoid feeling isolated in online classes.		2 (4.8%)	7 (16.7%)	22 (52.4%)	11 (26.2%)
21. I adopt various online activities to support my students' English language learning.		1 (2.4%)	9 (21.4%)	22 (52.4%)	10 (23.8%)
22. I stimulate my students' interest in learning the language in online classes through game-based learning.		2 (4.8%)	11 (26.2%)	21 (50%)	8 (19%)

Based on this study's research question; how does online learning affect students' motivation towards English language learning, the result can be concluded that teachers' encouragement and efforts in motivating students' English language learning in online classes turned out more positively. An average of 52% shows that teachers were motivate their students' English language learning very well in online classes. It can be seen clearly that teachers are exerting themselves to motivate their students' online learning with varied strategies and learning resources such as online learning tools, online platforms, game-based learning, the adaptation of authentic materials, praises, and rewards. 23.5% of the respondents felt neutral in motivating their students. While an average of 21.4% of the respondents shows that they were strongly supporting their student's English language learning in online classes. However, a very minimal average of 4.3% of the respondents were shown they were not agreed with the statements about motivating the student's English language learning online.

CONCLUSION

The researcher found that online teaching is possible affects students' motivation toward learning. The result indicated that sufficient online gamified learning tools and learning content with authentic materials can increase and motivate the students to learn the English language online. Some of the learning materials that can motivate students online learning include YouTube videos, Kahoot, Quizizz, Quizlet, Liveworksheet, Wordwall, etc. Apart from that, whether in online teaching or physical classroom praising and rewarding are the motivation factors for active and happy learning. A strategy that motivates the students' online learning, teachers agreed that they were praised and rewarded the students when performed well.

There are some limitations to this research study. Although the survey has provided insight on how online teaching motivates English language learning among primary students, the study has been done with a small sample of teachers from UNITAR International University as well as other schools. Thus, the findings were unable to provide the generalizations of this study. For the future study, a wider range of samples from various schools or institutions to determine the validity of these findings and provide more insight into motivation factors for online English language learning.

The study presented the findings of teachers' efforts and ability to motivate their students using varied online learning platforms and learning tools. With revised content and instructional strategies, teachers can create an active online learning environment. The study also revealed that technology competencies are vital for successful online teaching and learning. It is compulsory for the teachers whether, from the new or old generation, they must strengthen their technology skills to deliver the lesson successfully. Using creative teaching strategies and sufficient online resources helps to ensure that students' engagement while keeping their motivation towards online English language learning.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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